

METHODS OF ACETYLENE PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Acetylene is an important raw material in the chemical industry and is widely used in organic synthesis, as well as in the production of polymers, solvents, and fuel gases. This technology is characterized by energy efficiency, environmental safety, and high productivity. In addition, the production of hydrogen as a by-product increases the economic efficiency of the process.

Introduction. Acetylene (C₂H₂) is an important raw material in the chemical industry and is widely used in the production of organic synthesis products, polymers, solvents, and fuel gases. This thesis analyzes the main methods of acetylene production, their advantages and disadvantages, and identifies the most efficient technologies. Acetylene (HC≡CH) is the simplest hydrocarbon containing a carbon-carbon triple bond [1-2].

1. Calcium carbide method. Acetylene was first obtained in 1836 by E. Davy through the reaction of water with potassium acetylide (carbide) [Miller S. A., 1966]. In 1862, M. Berthelot produced HC≡CH by passing an electric arc between carbon and hydrogen. Following the discovery of the electrothermal method for producing calcium carbide by A. Moissan and T. L. in 1892, acetylene was obtained using the Willson reaction [3-4].

The calcium carbide (CaC₂) method is rarely used in modern industry due to the large amount of environmentally harmful emissions it generates.

2. Pyrolysis of methane and natural gas. Because of the high energy consumption associated with CaC₂ production, alternative methods for obtaining acetylene from natural gas and light hydrocarbons have been developed. As a result, acetylene is formed at temperatures of approximately ~1500 °C through the decomposition of methane and light hydrocarbons, as well as via the thermo-oxidative pyrolysis of methane according to the reaction:

In modern industry, the most widely used method involves the decomposition of methane at high temperatures:

The process is carried out at temperatures of 1500–1600 °C within a very short reaction time. This method is characterized by the use of cheap and widely available raw materials (natural gas), high productivity, low waste generation, and the possibility of continuous operation. However, it requires very high temperatures and complex technological control.

3. Electric arc and plasma methods. Electric arc and plasma-chemical methods are also used for acetylene production. The electrocracking of liquid hydrocarbons (the N. S. Pechuro method) is considered particularly effective and offers practical applicability. In these methods, hydrocarbons are decomposed using an electric arc or plasma. Although high-purity acetylene can be obtained, these processes are rarely applied on an industrial scale due to extremely high energy consumption.

Conclusion. Based on the requirements of modern chemical industry, methane pyrolysis is considered the most efficient method for acetylene production. This technology is distinguished by its energy efficiency, environmental safety, and high productivity. In addition, the formation of hydrogen as a by-product significantly increases the economic efficiency of the process. Although several methods for acetylene production exist and each can be applied under specific conditions, considering modern industrial demands and environmental requirements, methane pyrolysis is the most promising and effective technology. It is expected that this method will remain the primary direction for acetylene production in the future.

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